

MuHoW: Distributed protocol for resource sharing in collaborative edge-computing networks

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ABSTRACT

The incorporation of end devices in the edge-to-cloud continuum yields substantial benefits to conventional cloud computing frameworks, expediting communication between end devices and computational resources, and resulting in new use cases, particularly in the field of mobile networks. However, few related works leverage the full potential of resource sharing at the far edge, as most proposals require that end nodes rely on a higher-capacity computational node.

This manuscript presents Multi-Hop Wireless Resource Sharing Protocol (MuHoW), a lightweight protocol tailored for multi-hop wireless networks. MuHoW enables resource sharing within collaborative edge-computing networks by facilitating the discovery of wireless neighbours and subsequently establishing a confluence tree directed towards the edge/fog infrastructure. This tree serves as a conduit for aggregating essential resource sharing information, ensuring the establishment of a seamless collaborative edge/fog environment. The empirical findings highlight the scalability of MuHoW, due to its linear control message growth with network size. Moreover, the efficiency of the protocol is very high even in lossy environments as evidenced by the fact that most resource sharing messages are successfully delivered as expected.

1. Introduction

With the advent of cutting-edge technology and services, the demand for computation has skyrocketed. Therefore, novel computing models and architectures have emerged to address this issue effectively [1]. The cloud computing [2,3] is a revolutionary technology leveraging the capabilities of networked computers to mitigate the burden on single machines. The resulting platforms, or “clouds”, are comprised of large-scale data centres that offer substantial computational power, operational versatility, and scalability. Moreover, it is important to acknowledge the potential challenges that arise from their dispersion across different locations. The widespread adoption of these centres has led to communication lags and network congestion, which can hinder the performance of applications heavily reliant on such infrastructure since delays or bottlenecks can result in significant repercussions.

To address these issues, the scientific community has suggested several evolutionary approaches, including edge computing and fog computing. These technologies aim to move computational processes

closer to end users, thereby reducing the distance data must travel and mitigating the effects of communication lags and congestion. Edge Computing [4] is designed to bring computation and data storage closer to the edge of the network, while Fog Computing [5] extends this concept by also incorporating nodes at the edges of the network and decentralising the computing power, enabling faster and more efficient data processing in closer proximity to end devices. Hence, Fog Computing helps to provide reduced latency, improved resource utilisation, and enhanced scalability, which makes it an attractive option for a wide range of applications, particularly those involving real-time data processing and analysis. Both solutions present exciting opportunities for enhancing the efficiency and reliability of cloud/fog computing infrastructures.

In addition, the advent of emerging technologies such as 5G, 6G, industry 4.0, cloud-IoT, environmental monitoring, big data, smart cities, connected cars, autonomous driving, and smart energy has prompted the development of novel computing models, infrastructures and use-cases. These advancements will bring significant enhancements to a

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variety of services, while enabling networks to adapt to evolving technologies. To meet the highly sought-after features of efficient logistics and transportation, immediacy, reliability, and ease of scalability in these applications, the establishment of new computing frameworks is essential. Ultimately, these new models will serve as the foundation for innovative services and applications.

Focusing on the requirements to provide efficient edge and fog computing solutions, this paper presents MuHoW, a distributed lightweight protocol for resource sharing in collaborative edge-computing networks. Its purpose is to foster the collaboration between wireless devices at the far edge, letting them share their resources to perform the required tasks in the fastest and more efficient way and without requiring any central scheduler. Taking into account the previous existing related work summarised in Section 2, the main contributions behind MuHoW protocol are:

- The definition of a lightweight protocol for resource sharing considering low-capacity and low-energy devices. Its design considers:
 - Multi-hop support by supporting edge computing scenarios in which the sensor/nodes may be more than one-hop away from a gateway.
 - Distributed design without the existence of any central scheduler or similar entity.
 - Countermeasures to tackle with errors because of noisy wireless channels or mobile nodes.
- A detailed performance evaluation with the following characteristics:
 - Multi-hop wireless scenarios.
 - Large scales scenarios (up to 81 wireless nodes).
 - Emulation platform based on Mininet-WiFi [6].
 - Results with/without background traffic and packet losses.
- First multi-hop general distributed proposal validated in an emulated platform.
- The proposed design scales up because the protocol messages and convergence time grow linearly with the network size.
- Retransmission timers can handle high packet losses effectively because most nodes (95%–98%) can obtain the required status to adequately operate and share their resources with others (90%–98%).
- Source code available [7].

To the best of our knowledge, there is no other solution with distributed multi-hop support aim at constrained devices, which is key in emerging scenarios and use cases related to edge/fog computing.

This manuscript is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the related work in the field. In Section 3, the MuHoW protocol is presented. Section 4 evaluates the proposal itself. Finally, Section 5 summarises the conclusions of the research presented herein.

2. Related work

In the following paragraphs, we explore the related work from more generic to more specific to our proposal: starting with related surveys, followed by proposals in the field of resource management in fog/edge computing, then focusing on distributed proposals, and finally addressing multi-hop distributed resource management, which is the specific field to which our work belongs. Our intention is to provide a general overview of the state of the art, emphasising on similar works, which will be also qualitatively assessed at the end of this section. For that reason, the initial topics are briefly covered and only the specific one is thoroughly examined and compared with our proposal.

2.1. Related surveys and topics

In relation with MuHoW, diverse related works exist and particularly in the field of computer networking and focused on fog/edge computing. Some surveys already provide comprehensive summaries about task offloading [8–11], service placement [12–15], resource management [16–18], and load balancing [19] in fog/edge computing environments. Although named differently, the final objective is very similar, optimisation of resource location in that environment. In fact, most of these works rely on Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) techniques for this purpose.

2.2. Resource management in fog/edge computing

Delving into specific proposals related to the field of task offloading and task allocation, these could be defined as decision algorithm that select the best location (local, fog/edge or cloud) to deploy applications and/or services at each time.

Alsaffar et al. [20] present an architecture for service delegation for Internet-of-Things (IoT) environments, and their decision algorithm consider three parameters: service size, completion time and computing capacity of the node, or Virtual Machine (VM). Du et al. [21] present a game-based decision algorithm, while Zhou et al. [22] follow a contract-learning approach.

Regarding Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)-related parameters for optimisation, Wang et al. [23] introduce the need to consider energy consumption as part of the decision algorithm, while Alharbi et al. [24] study energy efficiency in the specific case of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) networks. Yadav et al. [25] also consider energy, but adding latency as another parameter, and focus on the specific case of vehicular fog computing, use case also covered by Tang et al. [26].

Some studies also evaluate the potential heterogeneity of use cases and infrastructures, as this is a key characteristic of the network edge. Beraldi et al. [27] perform load balancing decisions (i.e. serving of offloading a task) in heterogeneous fog infrastructures in smart cities, while Zhang et al. [28] centre their analysis on heterogeneous Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) wireless networks, and Tran-Dang et al. [29] do not highlight any specific use case but aim at delay minimisation in their decisions.

As aforementioned, most recent works employ AI/ML techniques for their algorithms, Li et al. [30], Ali et al. [31] and Naouri et al. [32] propose a learning approach for collaborative mobile edge computing. Baek et al. [33] using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), Shao et al. [34] focusing on a lightweight ML approach.

2.3. Distributed and collaborative fog/edge computing

Skarlat et al. [35] and Pinto et al. [36] are some of the first research proposals in the area of Collaborative Edge Computing (CEC), which considers the option to distribute resources among nodes (instead of selecting one specific node for offloading), for example, taking into consideration maximum delay or other user needs. Beraldi et al. [37] have a distributed mechanism to select the best fog node inspired by game theory. Also leveraging game theory, Chen et al. [38] define a distributed algorithm for dense small cells networks, which iteratively cooperate to perform task offloading decisions, and Smolka et al. [39] also define a decentralised algorithm that evaluates application execution time based on auctions. Zhang et al. [40] define an edge-native task scheduling system that extends Kubernetes (considered the de-facto platform in the field) to efficiently manage distributed and heterogeneous edge resources, dynamically evaluating task requirements and resource status. Wang et al. [41] define an algorithm for optimal service placement in edge computing that considers the impact of user interactions and mobility, and evaluate its using real-world data traces. Many other similar recent works exist [42–46]. In fact, Mann et al. [46]

classify these types of algorithms in four types: centralised, independent fogs, communicated fogs, and overlapped fogs (the latter three being distributed approaches).

Additionally, distributed task offloading could also be performed leveraging Device-to-Device (D2D) communications at the far edge [47–54]. Similarly to previous works, their objective functions envision energy efficiency [49], security [50], device heterogeneity [51], and their resource sharing could be based on blockchain [53] and serve different use cases, like Industrial IoT (IIoT) [54].

2.4. Multi-hop collaborative edge computing

In relation to the contributions of our protocol, few works explore the possibility of resource allocation in multi-hop CEC, those in which several intermediate nodes should be traversed to reach a gateway (node with higher resources or capacity).

As one of the first works, Hong et al. [55] investigate the option to use specific nodes as relays for task offloading in hierarchical IIoT edge computing environments. However, it does not specify to what extent the decision is performed jointly for all nodes and if nodes allow reallocating tasks far beyond one relay node. Moreover it does not consider partial task allocation either.

Implementing routing through multiple relay nodes and allowing partial task allocation, Sahni et al. [56] provide an integrated solution for task offloading in edge computing that takes into account synchronisation of tasks, among other parameters, to optimise the completion time. He et al. [57] focus on UAV networks and define an algorithm to accomplish both service placement and resource allocation at once, although it still does not consider dynamic changes of that placement. Kaneva et al. [58] leverages multi-hop edge computing to improve the efficiency in fog computing environments, using Reinforcement Learning (RL), and proving that single-hop approaches yield worse results even using more complex and optimised decision algorithms. Tran-Dang et al. [59] present DISCO, a distributed framework that reduces execution delay.

Focusing on specific use cases, and in the case of vehicular networks, Deng et al. [60] suggest that vehicular networks may assist as relay nodes to accelerate task offloading between one particular vehicle and a MEC server. One of the following works of the same authors try to generalise the idea by defining an alternative mechanism to leverage end nodes as relays to choose the best edge node to execute tasks [61]. Hussain et al. [62] leverages multi-hop edge computing to improve task offloading in vehicular networks, which benefit for these multi-hop networks as nodes move. Liu et al. [63] propose a scheme for vehicle-to-vehicle task offloading, in which one vehicle might offload a task to another one-hop or two-hop (if needed) neighbour vehicle.

In the case of UAV networks, Tong et al. [64] consider UAV might help in task offloading, but might not be able to compute a complete task on their own. For that reason, they propose a collaborative decision algorithm that is capable of distributing partial tasks to the UAVs and, later on, compose the result and provide it to the user that initially requested the task offloading. The UAV follow a dynamic hierarchy. He et al. [65] propose two algorithms for joint task offloading as well, one for ideal scenarios (equal link bandwidth and no interferences), and claim that it has linear growth and it can be implemented in a distributed manner. However, they do not include multiple users or servers in their definition. Ahmad et al. [66] define a framework, in which nodes are somehow hierarchically grouped, and describes different optimisation steps for the initial allocation of UAVs and their mobility afterwards. Finally, Hoa et al. [67] consider offloading in multi-hop UAV networks, not following any type of particular hierarchy, implementing a DRL algorithm.

Finally, in the case of satellite networks, Zhang et al. [68] present a computation peer offloading scheme for MEC-enabled satellite networks, in which satellites cooperate to distribute their workload. The

decision algorithm is presented as an offline global optimisation problem, which takes snapshots of the network to model its dynamics, and it is implemented as a distributed mechanism, so that each satellite is autonomous. The objective is to optimise both delay and energy. While this is the only related work that presents the option of a distributed implementation for multi-hop collaborative edge computing, the solution is still designed as a global optimisation problem, so it still requires a central component even if the procedure follows a decentralised approach afterwards.

2.5. Comparison summary and contributions of MuHoW

As previously stated, the closest works to MuHoW were presented in the previous subsection, which addresses multi-hop collaborative edge computing. For that reason, we chronologically summarised all works in Table 1, evaluating the implemented technique, design metrics, associated use case (if any or if a generalised proposal), type of implementation (distributed or centralised), evaluation tools, and available code. As it can be observed, only three works are generalised for any use case, almost all works are centralised, except one (which could be considered partially distributed), all works were either analytically evaluated or via simulation, few works were examined with topologies with more than 10 nodes, and none provides available code of their implementation.

Following the revision of related work, our proposal, accomplishes a missing gap in the state of the art; MuHoW is a distributed protocol (to the best of our knowledge, the first fully decentralised), generalised for any type of multi-hop edge computing scenario, and compatible with its implementation in constrained devices, those commonly located at the far edge of the network. Furthermore, our evaluation is based on an emulated environment (closer to reality), tested with almost 81 nodes, and our code is publicly available.

3. Definition of MuHoW

The key feature of the MuHoW protocol is the creation of a local map that allows each node to discover, share, and request resources in a distributed manner. This local map mainly contains information about neighbours, hence granting its size is independent of the total number of network nodes. Moreover, the information is labelled, so that multi-hop communications can be directly inferred from it.

The protocol relies on two periodic procedures (based on hierarchical labelling) for each network node to discover and identify its neighbours and to build a confluence tree rooted at the node designated as the network root (or gateway). This tree will set the direction of the resource demand/offer message exchange that the network nodes will carry out to build the target local map.

3.1. Status node diagram

According to the position of each node in the confluence tree, four possible states are considered: UNDEFINED, ROOT, MIDDLE and LEAF. A node will be in UNDEFINED state when it does not know its position in the tree. On the other hand, its state will be LEAF when it occupies the last position in a branch (furthest from the ROOT) and, finally, we will say that its state is MIDDLE when it is part of a branch, but it is neither ROOT nor LEAF.

Furthermore, in relation to the relative position of two contiguous nodes belonging to the same branch, we will say that a node is *Child* of the other when it is one hop further away from the ROOT than the other. Conversely, we will say that a node is *Parent* of the other when it is one hop closer to the ROOT.

After start-up, each node is self-assigned the UNDEFINED state and will remain in this state until it knows its relative position in the ROOT's confluence tree (and acquires the corresponding label that identifies it within the tree). Depending on the value of the label that identifies

Table 1
Comparison with related works and contributions of MuHoW.

Article	Year	Technique	Design metric	Use case	Implementation	Evaluation tools	Available code?
Zhang et al. [68]	2015	Optimisation problem	Delay and energy consumption	Satellite networks	Distributed	Simulation. 192 nodes	–
Hong et al. [55]	2019	Game theory	Computation time and energy consumption	IIoT networks	Centralised	Simulation. Up to 200 nodes. Performance measured in CPU cycles and relative values	–
Deng et al. [60]	2020	Binary search	Delay and computation cost	Vehicular networks	Centralised	Simulation	–
Sahni et al. [56]	2021	Optimisation problem	Completion time and algorithm running time	Generalised	Centralised	Simulation. Up to 25 nodes	–
He et al. [57]	2021	Optimisation problem	Task processing time	UAV networks	Centralised	Simulation. 5 nodes	–
Kaneva et al. [58]	2021	ML (RL)	Transmission time	Generalised	Centralised	Simulation. 10 nodes	–
Hussain et al. [62]	2021	Optimisation problem	Delay, hop limit and computation cost	Vehicular networks	Centralised	Simulation. Up to 700 nodes. Mobility patterns and real-world traces	–
Liu et al. [63]	2022	Optimisation problem	Delay	Vehicular networks	Centralised	Simulation	–
Tong et al. [64]	2022	Optimisation problem	Energy consumption	UAV networks	Centralised	Simulation. Up to 11 nodes	–
He et al. [65]	2022	Optimisation problem	Computation cost	UAV networks	Centralised	Simulation. Up to 8 nodes	–
Ahmad et al. [66]	2023	Optimisation problem	Delay, energy consumption, and reliability	UAV networks	Centralised	Simulation. Up to 10 nodes	–
Hoa et al. [67]	2023	ML (DRL)	Delay and energy consumption	UAV networks	Centralised	Simulation. 9 nodes	–
Tran-Dang et al. [59]	2023	Matching theory	Computation time	Generalised	Centralised	Simulation. 100 nodes	–
Deng et al. [61]	2023	Optimisation problem/Matching theory	Throughput	Generalised	Centralised	Analytical	–
Alvarez-Horcajo et al.	2024	Breadth first search	Delay, convergence time and reliability	Generalised	Distributed	Emulation. Up to 80 nodes	✓(GitHub)

its position in the tree and the labels that identify its neighbours (labels that will be assigned by one of the two aforementioned periodic procedures), it will decide whether to go to the MIDDLE state (if it detects at least one *Child* node) or LEAF (if it cannot classify any of its known neighbours as *Child*).

3.2. Behaviour of MuHoW

To illustrate the behaviour of the MuHoW protocol, we will use the example network shown in Fig. 1(a). It depicts a network composed of seven wireless nodes, named *W1* to *W7*, as well as the relative locations of these nodes and the corresponding coverage areas. The node *W1* is designated as the root node of the network.

In addition to the Neighbour Discovery and Tree Construction procedures already mentioned, the protocol is completed by two other procedures that deal with the management of resource requests and offers, and the recovery from errors due to noisy channels. In the following, each of these four procedures is explained in detail and exemplified in the example network.

3.2.1. Neighbour discovery

The Neighbour Discovery procedure (exemplified in Figs. 1(b) and 1(c)), is based on the periodic broadcast of Hello messages (see Fig. 2(a)). Each Hello message identifies the node sending the message by a *Layer2* address (e.g. a Media Access Control (MAC) address) so that other nodes within range of the sender can detect and identify it.

Each time a node receives a Hello message from a neighbour, it must store this information in its Neighbour Table including the sender's address together with a locally assigned identifier (an integer) to that node and a timestamp. Table 2 shows the content of the Neighbour Table that will build the *W3* node as an example. Hello messages are distinguished from other messages in the protocol by a specific Option Code field (*0x01*).

3.2.2. Confluence tree construction

After a fixed time designed to allow for the discovery procedure, the root node (*W1*) self-assigns the root tree label (*1.*) and triggers the Confluence Tree Construction procedure by broadcasting a *SetTree* message (see Fig. 2(b)) to its neighbours. Apart from its own tree label (*1.*), each message includes a specific Option Code field (*0x02*), a Sequence Number field (to distinguish it from subsequent *SetTree* messages) and as many tuples $\langle \text{Neighbour MAC address, Neighbour local ID} \rangle$ as neighbours of *W1* are in its Neighbour Table (according to Table 2 these are $\langle W1, 1. \rangle$, $\langle W3, 2. \rangle$ and $\langle W4, 3. \rangle$ in the example network). The Confluence Tree Construction procedure works in a periodic manner. A new *SetTree* message, with increasing sequence number, will be broadcast every *SetTree_T0* seconds.

When this message is received by a neighbour of the root node, it immediately designates the sender as its *Parent* node. Then, the node also extracts (from the message) the tree label identifying the sender of the message and the local ID of the tuple containing the receiver's own address, as together they compose a new tree label that will correspond to the receiving node. In the example, nodes *W2*, *W3* and *W4* will

Fig. 1. Neighbour Discovery in the example topology.

Fig. 2. MuHoW control messages.

receive the *SetTree* message from *W1* (*root*), whose tree label is *1.*, and build their own tree label, resulting in *1.1.* for *W2*, *1.2.* for *W3* and *1.3.* for *W4*. All this information is added to the Neighbour Table as shown in Table 3. Finally, the node generates and broadcast its own *SetTree* message (e.g. *W4* will send a message with *1.3.* as tree label and three neighbour tuples $\langle W1, 1.\rangle$, $\langle W3, 2.\rangle$ and $\langle W7, 3.\rangle$).

If the receiving node has only one known neighbour it automatically transits to the LEAF state. On the contrary, if it has several neighbours, it must wait to receive a copy of the original *SetTree* message from each of them before deciding which state to transit to (MIDDLE or LEAF). In this case, when it receives the second and successive copies, the node will already have an assigned tree label and will process the received message differently depending on the duplicate message management criteria used, for example, a *Fastest Path* or *Shortest Path* (number of hops) criterion.

Table 2

Neighbour table after neighbour discovery (*W1*).

Address	Id	TimeStamp
W2	1	T1
W3	2	T2
W4	3	T3

Table 3

Neighbour table after tree construction (*W3*).

Address	Id	Label received	Relationship	TimeStamp
W1	1	1.2	Parent	T1
W2	2	1.1.3	None	T2
W4	3	1.3.2	None	T3
W5	4	1.2.2.2	Child	T4
W6	5	1.3.3.3.2	None	T5
W7	6	1.3.3.2	None	T6

Fastest Path criterion In this case, the node keeps the tree label assigned by the first *SetTree* message received, while newer labels assigned by the second and successive *SetTree* messages (late messages) are simply stored within the Neighbour Table. Second and successive copies of a *SetTree* message are processed but not broadcast.

When the tree label received in the *SetTree* message contains the node's own tree label as a prefix, the neighbour that sent it is marked as *Child* and, finally, once the messages from all the neighbours have been processed, the status is changed to LEAF if none of the neighbours has been recognised as *Child*, or set to MIDDLE otherwise. Fig. 3(a) shows a possible application of this criterion in the example network with the assigned tree labels, while Fig. 3(b) represents the resulting tree, in which it can be observed that *W3*, *W4* and *W7* are MIDDLE nodes and *W2*, *W5* and *W6* are LEAF nodes. The right-most branch of the tree is clearly the fastest one so *W6* joins *W7* instead of joining *W3* or *W5* which are one hop closer to the root.

Shortest Path criterion Following this criterion, the node discards the previously assigned tree label if it receives one with fewer hops to the ROOT (which can be easily inferred from the length of the tree label). In such a case, in addition to processing the *SetTree* message, a new *SetTree* must be generated and broadcast. Moreover, all the information in the Neighbour Table related to the old tree label must be updated or removed such as the *Parent* mark and the labels of its neighbours. The node status must also be reset to UNDEFINED. If the node has more than one neighbour it will wait for the information from all of them before deciding its new state, or transit to LEAF otherwise. Fig. 4(a) shows a possible application of this criterion in the example network with the assigned tree labels, while Fig. 4(b) represents the resulting tree where it can be observed that, unlike the previous case, *W7* is now a LEAF node and each node in the network is located at the minimum hop distance from the root.

3.2.3. Resource information sharing

In contrast to the label assignment process (tree construction) which takes place in the direction from root to leaves, the resource sharing process takes place in the opposite direction, from leaves to root. In this way, the aggregation of shareable resources takes place on the way to the root. The root actually acts as a gateway to the network in case the resource balance is negative and resources are required from the outside.

This is an asynchronous process, once a node has acquired the LEAF status, it begins the process of exchanging resource information (demands/offers). To do so, it constructs and sends a Load message (see Fig. 2(c)) to its *Parent* node.

The Load message comprises a *Layer 2 header*, followed by the Option Code field with a value of "0x03" and the Load Sign field indicating whether the node requires resources (with a minus sign) or can share resources (with a plus sign). Subsequently, the message

Fig. 3. Example of tree construction in an ideal environment (Fastest Path criterion).

Fig. 4. Example of tree construction in an ideal environment (Shortest Path criterion).

Fig. 5. Example of the resource sharing procedure.

contains the Load Value field, representing the number of resources that the node can share or require. And finally, the Absolute Value field, which indicates the cumulative value (in absolute values) of the loads (demand/supply) indicated by that node and all its descendants in the tree. In the case of a LEAF node, this value is the same as the Load Value field.

When a MIDDLE node receives a Load message, it stores the indicated Load Value (together with the sign) in its Neighbour Table and waits until it has received a similar message from each of its Child nodes to load balance all the nodes below it in the tree in addition to its own. With this information it constructs a new Load message and sends it to its own Parent node. This process continues until all Load messages converge at the ROOT node.

Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) show the Load message exchange corresponding to the trees constructed in Figs. 3 (fastest path) and 4 (shortest path).

3.2.4. Recovery procedures

In non-ideal environments, message loss could affect normal operation, so our protocol defines mechanisms designed to detect and mitigate this problem. They are mainly based on the use of timers to detect possible losses.

The loss of a SetTree message could block the transit from UNDEFINED to the MIDDLE or LEAF state and the sending of the Load message itself as the criterion of having received a Load message from all Child nodes would never be met. To deal with this problem, the Status_TO timer has been included. If this timer expires and the node is still in UNDEFINED state, it is automatically changed to LEAF and the corresponding Load message is sent to the Parent node. In the same way, if the timer expires and a MIDDLE node has not yet received the Load messages from all its Child nodes, the information corresponding to the incomplete Child nodes is deleted from the Neighbour Table and the Load message is sent without this information. Also, the loss of a SetTree message may lead to unnoticed Child nodes if the message from the Child is not received at the corresponding Parent; hence, unexpected Load messages from an unnoticed Child may be received at a Parent node. In this scenario, the receiving node updates its Neighbour Table to include the new Child node, recalculates the load balance, and sends a Load message to its Parent node.

Likewise, the loss of a Load message could block the Resource Sharing procedure. To deal with this problem, every Load message must be acknowledged by the receiving node before the Load_TO timer expires. Fig. 2 shows the structure of a LoadACK message. If this timer expires before the corresponding ACK is received the Load message is resent.

Fig. 6 shows the recovery against the loss of the SetTree message (from W5 to W2) under the Shortest Path criterion. We can see that since W5 cannot be identified as a Child (due to the loss of the SetTree message) W2 cannot switch to the LEAF state (see Figs. 6(a) and 6(b)) until its Status_TO timer expires. After that, the exchange of messages for resource sharing takes place (see Fig. 6(c)).

Similarly, Fig. 7 shows the recovery from the loss of the Load message from W7 to W4. In this case, W4 sends its own Load message information to W1 without waiting for W7 (see Fig. 7(b)). After the corresponding timeout, W7 resends the Load message (not being acknowledged by W4). Then, W4 recalculates its new load balance (including the information sent by W7) and sends it back to W1 (see Fig. 7(c)).

3.3. MuHoW flowcharts and timers

In order to summarise MuHoW behaviour, this section includes three flow charts that describe the actions performed by the protocol logic at a node.

The chart in Fig. 8 shows the initialisation of a node, which includes the status definition (either UNDEFINED or ROOT), and the starting point of the Neighbour Discovery and the Tree Construction processes.

The diagram in Fig. 9 shows the processing of a protocol message received at a node. It is divided into four distinct parts designed to deal with the processing of a protocol message (either Hello, SetTree, Load or LoadACK). The first part (in yellow) on the left most part of the figure is activated upon the reception of a Hello message in order to build the Neighbour Table. Next to it, the blue zone shows

Fig. 6. Example of recovery from a SetTree message loss (sent from W5 to W2).

Fig. 7. Example of recovery from a Load message loss (from W7 to W4).

the processing of a SetTree message which sets the Status, the tree label and the Parent/Child relation of nodes in the tree. Then, the green zone of the figure explains the processing of a Load message to build the resource sharing map. And on the right most part, the purple one, which is responsible for the processing of a LoadACK message.

Fig. 8. Starting flowchart of MuHoW.

Finally, Fig. 10 summarise the operations performed at a node upon a protocol timer expiration. There are four timers embedded in the protocol. Two of them control the periodicity of the protocol: the Hello_TO controls the periodic exchange of Hello messages so that the nodes can discover and update their neighbours, and the SetTree_TO which periodically triggers the broadcast of a SetTree message to start the construction of a new tree. And the other two are included to deal with network losses: the Status_TO designed to overcome the loss of SetTree messages, which prevents the convergence of the protocol (the construction of the tree and the sharing of resource information), and the Load_TO designed to confirm the reception of Load messages.

The timers set in MuHoW are configured as follows:

- Hello_TO: a 3 s timeout designed to periodically update the wireless neighbour list.
- SetTree_TO: a 3 s timeout designed to periodically build a new confluence tree. Its value is aligned to the Hello_TO.
- Load_TO: a 500 millisecond timeout designed to allow application-level retransmission of Load messages after the link layer completes its back-off retransmission procedure [69].
- Status_TO: a variable timeout (ranging from 50 to 500 ms). Its maximum value is aligned with the Load_TO. Neighbour nodes of the Root are assigned the maximum value. Other nodes are assigned decreasing values according to the number of hops to the ROOT in steps of 50 ms. This setup allows enough time for the process of distributing the SetTree messages down the tree to the leaf nodes, calculating the balances and sending the corresponding Load message up the tree in each node.

4. Evaluation

The evaluation of the MuHoW protocol was conducted using an infrastructure comprising multiple hosts equipped with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 processors and 16 GB of RAM. To emulate diverse topologies, Mininet-WiFi [6] was utilised. The experiments were iterated ten times, and the outcomes for each run were averaged, followed by the computation of mean and 95% confidence interval values.

The experiment employs the Berlin, Leipzig, and Quasy-mesh wireless topologies [70], randomly selecting the ROOT node. The tests are mainly conducted on the Berlin and Leipzig topologies with 40, 60, and 80 nodes, in an ideal environment (neither background traffic nor losses). Both topologies have been created using the NPart tool [70]. These topologies are depicted in Fig. 11. The study also uses Quasy-mesh topologies with 25 nodes (5x5), 49 nodes (7x7), and 81 nodes (9x9) (shown in Fig. 12) for environment tests with simulated background traffic and no losses, as well as tests with simulated background traffic and losses, to ensure diversity of paths between the root node and other

Fig. 9. Main flowchart of MuHoW.

nodes. This is because the *Berlin* and *Leipzig* topologies exhibit great linearity, resulting in non-significant differences between both fastest and shortest path criteria.

Regarding the allocation of resources in each node, it followed a uniform distribution with average equal to zero and a range of values from -10 to 10. A minus value indicates that the node demands resources, while a positive value indicates the node's capacity to share/offer resources up to the assigned value.

The obtained results are not compared with previous solutions since, as explained in Section 2, MuHoW is the first multi-hop general distributed protocol for resource sharing in collaborative edge-computing networks.

4.1. No background traffic and no losses tests

The evaluation of MuHoW performance in this scenario involved several measures including the count of *SetTree*, *Load*, and *Load-ACK* messages. Additionally, average and absolute values were calculated to determine the balance of shared resources and how they could

be moved throughout the network until reaching the ROOT. Finally, the Convergence Time, the Mean Label Distribution Time, and the Resource Information Sharing time were measured. The former represents the time used by the protocol for distributing labels and receiving resource information, while the latter two denote the total time devoted to assign labels to all nodes and receive all network resource information at ROOT, respectively.

The aforementioned measures are depicted in Fig. 13, in graphs organised in two columns and three rows. The outcomes of the *Berlin* topology are placed in the left column, while the *Leipzig* topology results are presented in the right column. At the same time, the rows illustrate the three different metric evaluated for each topology. The top row displays the message count, followed by the number of shared resources in the second row, and the time metric in the bottom one.

The results indicate that the average number of packets linearly increases with the number of nodes, regardless of the topology employed (*Berlin* or *Leipzig*). Additionally, it is noteworthy that the Total Messages value aligns with the sum of the Load, ACK, and *SetTree* messages. Furthermore, the Convergence Time of the protocol also exhibits a linear increase with the number of nodes.

Fig. 10. Flowchart of timer functions of MuHoW.

(a) Quasi-Mesh 5x5 topology

(b) Quasi-Mesh 5x5 NPART plot

(c) Quasi-Mesh 7x7 topology

(d) Quasi-Mesh 7x7 NPART plot

(e) Quasi-Mesh 9x9 topology

(f) Quasi-Mesh 9x9 NPART plot

Fig. 12. Topologies for tests with losses.

(a) Berlin Topology on Mininet

(b) Berlin NPART plot

(c) Leipzig Topology on Mininet

(d) Leipzig NPART plot

Fig. 11. Topologies for ideal tests.

Fig. 13. Performance on Berlin and Leipzig topologies with no background traffic and no losses.

Fig. 14. Performance on Quasi-Mesh topologies with background traffic and no losses.

It is important to note that the Total Convergence time is lower than the time used for the distribution of the tree labels during the Tree Construction phase plus the time required to relay the information about shared resources to the ROOT. This is due to the concurrent occurrence of the Resource Information Sharing and Tree Construction phases, rather than sequentially.

Finally, the middle row in the figure indicates that the signed balance of shared resources is close to zero. This outcome was anticipated because of the use of a random allocation of resources of zero mean and the absence of any losses in the test environment.

4.2. Background traffic but no losses tests

The following paragraph discusses new environment tests that simulate background traffic by introducing random delays in the output queues of nodes to evaluate the performance of MuHoW under non-ideal conditions. The study focuses on comparing the different tree label assignment criteria explained in Section 3.2.2. The results are presented in Fig. 14. The same measurement parameters were used as in the previous environment. However, differently from the previous tests, the evaluated network is a Quasy-mesh, and the reason for it is that Berlin and Leipzig topologies are not so connective and yielded very similar results when simulating background traffic. The Quasy-mesh provides a higher number of alternative paths and facilitated the comparison of the two criteria with background traffic.

The top row of Fig. 14 shows that, when using the Shortest Path criterion for distribution, there is an increase in the number of SetTree messages since nodes that change their label require their neighbour nodes to broadcast new information. Conversely, when using the Fastest Path criterion, nodes only broadcast the first SetTree message received. The signed resourced balance shown in the middle row of the graphs confirms the network's resource distribution, with values close to zero due to the uniform distribution function used to assign resource values to each node. Finally, the bottom row indicates that, while both criteria produce similar results, the Shortest Path criterion results in a slight increase due to changes in the number of SetTree messages, which slows down the protocol execution.

Fig. 15. Performance on quasi-mesh topologies with background traffic and losses, without loss mitigation mechanisms.

4.3. Background traffic and losses tests

The main difference between these tests and the previous ones is the presence of message losses at the application layer, ranging from 0.5%, 1%, and 2%, which means packet error probabilities at the link layer of up to 57%. Additionally, background traffic was simulated by introducing random delays in the output queues of each node. Figs. 15 and 16 depict the results of these tests without and with loss mitigation mechanisms implemented, respectively.

Fig. 15 shows the results obtained without implementing loss mitigation mechanisms. This two-column figure displays the outcomes of applying the Fastest Path and the Shortest Path criteria while the information in rows represents the percentage of non UNDEFINED nodes and the percentage of shared resources, in relation to the ideal case.

The results indicate that, as the application-level losses increase, there is an increase in the number of UNDEFINED nodes (that means a reduction in the number of nodes that do not reach MIDDLE or LEAF states, i.e., non UNDEFINED nodes) and the corresponding decrease in the count of shared resources. Notably, the number of non UNDEFINED nodes is reduced to values around 75% while the count of shared resources is reduced to values around 30% in comparison to the no losses tests for the worst case (2% losses and 9x9 quasi-mesh nets). There is a significant impact of the size of the network: the larger the network, the greater the reduction in the percentage of UNDEFINED nodes and, above all, the greater the reduction in the shared resources count. This is because in larger networks the resulting tree branches are longer; therefore, the loss of a Load message next to the ROOT results in the loss of all information from the affected branches. Regarding the Fastest Path or the Shortest Path criteria there are no significant differences.

Finally, Fig. 16, compares the results obtained in three different situations: (i) no loss mitigation mechanisms, (ii) with only the Status_TO and (iii) with both the Status_TO and the Load message confirmation mechanism implemented, in quasi-mesh topologies. It is

Fig. 16. Performance comparison with and without loss mitigation mechanisms.

organised in the same way as Fig. 15 (the first two bars, the blue and red ones, are the same for ease of comparison). It can be observed that, by using `Status_TD`, almost 100% of the nodes reach the desired status (they transit from UNDEFINED to MIDDLE or LEAF) in all cases. The Shared Resources count, on the other hand, recovers to a large extent, although it still remains at values between 80% and 90% of the ideal case in the largest networks. However, if the Load message acknowledgement mechanism is also implemented, the recovery of the Shared Resources count is almost complete even in large networks (with only a single retry).

5. Conclusion

This paper presented MuHoW, a novel solution for resource sharing in collaborative edge-computing networks. As key contributions, MuHoW is distributed, supports multi-hop networks, and its decisions consume few computational resources and are generated fast enough for highly mobile devices at the far edge. This functionality is achieved in four steps: (1) A Neighbour Discovery mechanism (Section 3.2.1) that allows to periodically discover the neighbours of wireless nodes; (2) a confluence tree (Section 3.2.2) rooted in edge/fog devices and based on hierarchical labelling is built to allow an orderly communication among the wireless nodes towards the edge/fog infrastructure; (3) once a confluence tree is available, wireless nodes can communicate their resource requirements (request or offering of resources), which are locally aggregated and transmitted hop-by-hop until the root (Section 3.2.3); and (4) recovery mechanisms to deal with losses (Section 3.2.4).

The proposed solution is scalable since the number of required messages and the convergence time grows linearly with the number of nodes (see Figs. 13 and 14). Furthermore, the recovery mechanisms, even in the worst-case scenario (2% of losses at the application level), grants that 98% of the nodes successfully join the tree regardless of the tree construction criteria (see Fig. 16). Accordingly, the percentage of shared resources increases substantially (up to 80%–95% of ideal case) if the recovery mechanisms are activated (also in Fig. 16).

These results demonstrate the robustness of MuHoW, which facilitate distributed and collaborative resource sharing in edge/fog computing environments, and it is particularly suitable for constrained devices located at the far edge.

As future work, we envision the design and analysis of alternative path selection criteria, as well as its analysis in real constrained boards implementing some type of application that requires resource sharing (for example, AI/ML algorithms). Additionally, we would also like to examine its potential integration in the ETSI constrained MEC initiative [71] and its compatibility with the latest 3GPP releases, which include the EDGEAPP architecture [72].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Joaquin Alvarez-Horcajo: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Isaias Martinez-Yelmo:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Elisa Rojas:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Juan A. Carral:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Victoria Noci-Luna:** Data curation, Software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.hola

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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